
37. Ultra-wide binaries

BINARY STARS, as well as triple or even higher multiplicity star systems, are common. They form, in the swirling gas clouds of dense regions of the interstellar medium, over a very wide range of separations.

Binaries with very close separations can eventually spiral in and merge, while those formed with wider separations, and less weakly bound, can eventually be broken apart, either due to close stellar encounters (for example in star clusters), or as a result of numerous distant passages that incrementally pull on the binary, and it slowly evolves from being bound to being unbound.

Indeed, the wider their separation, the more easily they are disrupted, whether by passing stars, molecular clouds, or the Galaxy's spiral arms. Indicative survival times are of order a billion years at 0.1 pc separation (20 000 au, or 0.3 light-years), and perhaps around 100 million years at 0.5 pc (100 000 au, or 1.6 light-years).

ALTHOUGH THERE is no precise definition, we can refer to those with separations of 100–2000 au as 'wide' binaries, and those above about 30 000 au as 'ultra-wide'. At these enormous separations, the two stars will be very widely separated on the sky, by a degree or more, with very long orbital periods, but sharing an almost identical space motion over millennia.

How can two stars be recognised as a physical pair? Close binaries will often be unusually close together on the sky, much closer than the average star density. Monitoring their space motions or radial velocities over years or decades can reveal their orbital motion, and so confirm their gravitational connection.

But how can a wide or ultra-wide binary be distinguished from two completed unrelated stars? The orbital motion of a very wide-separation binary requires extremely accurate measurements to recognise. Indeed, the wider a binary is, the more difficult it is to identify – and this has been a major barrier to discovering and studying wide binaries in the past.

As an example of the situation pre-Gaia, a programme aimed at identifying wide binaries in the Galactic halo found less than 100 candidate pairs from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (Coronado et al., 2018).

GAIA IS IDENTIFYING many thousands of very wide and ultra-wide binaries from their highly accurate space motions. Essentially, a very widely separated binary can be recognised if both components share identical, or very similar, distances and space motions.

The resulting discoveries are allowing great progress in understanding their formation, evolution, and the various processes that contribute to their eventual disruption. I will look here at some advances enabled by Gaia DR1 and DR2 across a rather wide range of topics.

THE PARALLAXES AND proper motions of Gaia DR2 allowed El Badry & Rix (2018) to compile a catalogue of more than 50 000 wide binaries, in the separation range 50–50 000 au, and lying within 200 pc of the Sun.

While its sheer size is impressive, more interesting is the make-up of the resulting binary population. More than 50 000 are pairs of main-sequence stars, with a typical age of around 3 Gyr, while more than 3000 are pairs comprising a main-sequence primary star and a white dwarf secondary. And nearly 400 systems consist of white dwarf–white dwarf pairs.

In terms of numbers versus separation, a marked difference between the three populations is evident. The main sequence–main sequence binaries are reasonably consistent with a single power-law of slope over separations 500–50 000 au, while the main sequence–white dwarf, and white dwarf–white dwarf binaries, show distinct breaks at 3000 and 1500 au, respectively.

These distributions can be explained if the white dwarfs receive a 'kick' of about 0.75 km s^{-1} during their formation, presumably due to asymmetric mass-loss.

STARS BORN together should be chemically homogeneous, and wide binary systems provide an opportunity to test this assumption. For 25 systems comprising main-sequence stars of similar spectral type in Gaia DR2, Hawkins et al. (2020) obtained high-resolution spectra to derive chemical abundances for various elemental classes, including iron-peak and α -elements.

Twenty pairs (80%) were found to be homogeneous in [Fe/H], as well as in all other elemental abundances. That true physical pairs are more chemically homogeneous than random pairs of similar spectral type, provides another route to characterising very wide binaries.

GAIA DR2 has been used to examine the eccentricity distributions of wide binaries. This is of interest because their orbits provide a fossil record of their formation and early dynamical evolution. Specifically, the direction and speed of their relative motions contain statistical information on their eccentricities, which is typically inaccessible due to their long orbital periods.

Tokovinin (2020) used the 50 000 wide binary catalogue of El Badry & Rix (2018) to show that the eccentricity distribution is close to that expected from dynamical interactions within their natal cluster environment.

He found that pairs with projected separations below 200 au are more circular, a result expected where forces due to tides or gas friction have been operating. He found that wide pairs, above 1000 au, have an excess of very eccentric orbits, along the lines predicted by stellar ejections from unstable triple systems.

AIMING TO examine how the wide binary populations observed in star-forming regions or OB associations compare with that in the field Deacon & Kraus (2020) used the Gaia DR2 data to show that the wide binary population in the Alpha Per, Pleiades, Praesepe, and Hyades open clusters is significantly lower than the wide binary fraction observed in the field population.

However for two groups of young stars that likely originated in looser associations (young moving groups and the Pisces–Eridanus stream), the wide binary fraction was similar to, or even above, that of the field.

THE OCCURRENCE of binary stars at the largest separations has long been recognised as an important potential probe of the possible existence of Massive Compact Halo Objects (MACHOs) in the Galactic halo.

Tian et al. (2020) constructed samples of ultrawide binaries in the solar neighborhood, with separations 0.01–1 pc, using Gaia DR2 to define kinematic populations according to their tangential velocities, i.e., disk-like ($V_{\perp} < 40 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), intermediate, and halo-like ($V_{\perp} > 85 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) binaries, with thousands in each sample.

Fitting power laws to the separation distribution, they found that its slope at 300–10 000 au is the same

for all subpopulations, while it steepens at larger separations, an effect increasing with age.

They argued that the trends are contrary to that expected if the steepening at wide separations was due to gravitational perturbations by molecular clouds or stars (which would preferentially disrupt disk binaries), or to MACHOs (which would require a population inconsistent with other constraints). Instead, they could model the distribution of wide binaries as having been formed in dissolving star clusters, with the steepening at larger separations due to the finite size of the birth clusters.

ULTRA-WIDE SYSTEMS provide an interesting laboratory for testing the predictions of general relativity, and comparing them with the predictions of modified theories, like MOND, which have been put forward as an alternative to ‘dark matter’. At separations beyond about 5000 au, the stars in such a system have sufficiently small orbital accelerations that they can be used as a direct probe of binary orbits in low-gravity regimes.

Several such tests have been carried out with the Gaia data, and the statistical properties do show some anomalies. Others have suggested that these can be attributed to hidden triple systems. This subject is treated separately elsewhere.

THE IMPORTANCE of binaries in the formation of planetary nebulae, which form at the end of life of intermediate-mass stars, is well established. Binarity can explain the frequent occurrence of asymmetrical nebulae, and the formation of bipolar lobes. But establishing the incidence of binarity has not been easy.

González-Santamaría et al. (2020) used the extremely precise measurement of parallaxes and proper motions in Gaia DR2 to search for wide binary companions, out to around 20 000 au from the central stars of 211 planetary nebulae.

They found wide binary companions for eight of the sample, all with projected separations less than 15 000 au. They concluded that binarity plays a role, but that the Gaia DR3 release would be needed to expand the search to objects located closer to the central star.

IN THE FIELD of exoplanetary science, there is an ongoing debate as to whether the host stars of massive closely-orbiting ‘hot Jupiter’ planets are more likely to be found in wide binaries with separations above 100 au. A search for comoving, very wide companions with separations 1000–10 000 au was made by Hwang et al. (2020). They found that only around 10% of hot Jupiter hosts have companions at this sort of separation.

Their preliminary conclusion is that the formation of ‘hot Jupiter’ planets is not particularly sensitive to this sort of binarity, but improved Gaia data will clarify the picture further.